
NEED OF TRAINING FOR ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN PRIVATE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES

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Abstract-

The training is need of organizational development. Without training organization cannot perform smoothly and perfectly, to be with competitive world there is need of training and development. Day by day new and advance changes are occurring and to meet them the skilled force must be well trained and educated. Thus this paper focuses on the importance and need of training and development for the organizational development in private manufacturing industries.

Introduction-

From olden days training has been given more importance, in olden days before British period Indian culture was engaged in handicraft good, due to well known to about skill therefore more importance was given to trained employees because handicraft good were used to export in other country. During British period most of handicraft goods manufacturing were vanished this was due to industrialization. The introduction of machinery to Indian culture was introduced. From then need of skilled worker were in great demand to handle machinery work, therefore training to the employee were given for perfection to handle machinery and produced best quality of products. During this period British also opened many more vocational technical schools for industrial training.

Day by day there has been more emphasis is given on the employees training because they are essential for organizational development. There are some definition has been given by famous author.

Pigors, Myers & Malm (1969), Training is a planned continuous process with a need for periodic review combining evaluation of past results and analysis of future needs.

Goldstein & Ford (2002), Training is defined as the systematic acquisition of skills, rules, concepts or attitudes that results in improved performance in another environment.

Thus training is act of learning skills, this skill are essential for handling work. This skill help them the handle work efficiently and to produce high quality of product and also increase production. Training helps to have perfection in work, low wastage and have organizational cost saving. Thus training in need and important for organizational development, therefore every organization must conduct training and development program for their employees.

Objectives of the study

1) To study the practical implementation of training & development activities in private manufacturing industries in Dhule district.

Hypothesis of the study

1) Training and development result into organizational cost saving & improving individual performance.

Tools of Data Collection-

- **Primary Data** - With the help of Questionnaire, Observation & Field Survey.
- **Secondary Data** – From journal, research paper.

Sample size-

The sample size has been selected from Dhule industrial area. As Dhule district is being developing day by day due to implementation of heavy industry and for such there is need of skilled workforce. For the study 2 private manufacturing industries has been selected to assess the effectiveness of implementation of training & development in manufacturing industries. From 2 private manufacturing industries 10 employees from each industries has been selected.

Tools of Data Analysis –

Data is being collected with the help of questionnaire and collected data is being analysis with the help of stastical tools such as ‘Chi square test’ has been use

• Training and development result into organizational cost saving.

Training helps to have organizational cost saving, this is possible only when there are skilled worker, have knowledge of work accurately, such worker will make less mistake and less wastage, which will lead to have cost saving.

Sr. No	Response	Total	Percentage
1	Yes	17	85
2	No	03	15
Total	-	20	100

Collected data is being analysed with the help of chi-square test.

	Yes	No	Total
Fo	17	03	20
Fe	10	10	20
(Fo-Fe)	07	-7	-
(Fo-Fe)²	49	49	-
(Fo-Fe)²/Fe	4.9	4.9	9.8

Chi Square $X^2 = 9.8$

Calculated value of $X^2=9.8$

Fo - Frequency Observed

Fe - Frequency Expected

Degree of Frequency (df) = 1

Observations-

Level of Significance at 0.050 $X^2 = 3.84$

Calculated $X^2 =9.8$

$9.8 > 3.84$

Level of Significance at 0.010 $X^2 = 6.63$

Calculated $X^2 =9.8$

$9.8 > 6.63$

Thus, after analysing data with help of chi-square, it is found that hypothesis is tested and it is valid and accepted that ‘Training and development result into organizational cost saving’.

• Training increase ‘Individual Performance’

Training helps to learn the skills which are necessary for performing work, when there is availability of knowledge of work; employees can perform perfectly and helps to increase individual performance.

Sr. No	Response	Total	Percentage
1	Yes	18	90
2	No	02	10
Total	-	20	100

Collected data is being analysed with the help of chi-square test.

	Yes	No	Total
Fo	18	02	20
Fe	10	10	20
(Fo-Fe)	08	-08	-
(Fo-Fe)²	64	64	-
(Fo-Fe)²/Fe	6.4	6.4	12.8

Chi Square $X^2 = 12.8$

Calculated value of $X^2=12.8$

Fo - Frequency Observed

Fe - Frequency Expected

Degree of Frequency (df) = 1

Observations-

Level of Significance at 0.050 $X^2 = 3.84$

Calculated $X^2 = 12.8$

$12.8 > 3.84$

Level of Significance at 0.010 $X^2 = 6.63$

Calculated $X^2 = 12.8$

> 6.63

Thus, after analysing data with help of chi-square, it is found that hypothesis is tested and it is valid and accepted that 'Training and development increase Individual Performance'.

Conclusion-

After the data is being collected with help of questionnaire and being analysed with help of statistical tools, it is found that training is necessary for the organizational development, thus, implemented training program by private manufacturing industries, helped them to have organizational cost saving at the same time it helps them to increase the individual performance among employees. Therefore training is need of organizational development.

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